

Porting a Java-based Brain Simulation Software to C++

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Project Specification

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The brain is an extremely complex system, consisting of approximately 100 billion neurons that are connected to one another. The way these neurons are structured allows for very efficient and robust function. For example, human face recognition outperforms any currently available machine algorithm. One way to better understand this complex structure is to elucidate how it arises during development. The improvements in computing technology in the last few years have made it possible to use large-scale computer simulations to investigate such developmental processes. However, the appropriate software that can fully exploit the potentials of the state-of-the-art hardware remains to be implemented.

Figure 0.1: A neuronal branch generated in simulation using the simulation framework Cx3D.

A currently available software solution to simulate neural development is Cx3D. (<https://www.ini.uzh.ch/~amw/seco/cx3d/>). However, this software is Java-based, and not ideal for high-performance computing (HPC). In order to adapt Cx3D to support HPC, a software that has similar functionalities as Cx3D but is coded in C++ is needed.

Roman Bauer

Abstract

This report describes the process of porting the Java-based Brain Simulation Software Cortex3D (Cx3D) to C++. Cx3D was originally developed in Java, which is not ideal for high-performance computing. This is the first step towards the goal to create a software to simulate richer and deeper structures of the brain. An iterative porting approach has been chosen for this task. This means, that one Java class is translated at each iteration. After the C++ representation of this class has been created, it replaces the Java version. Interfacing C++ code from Java is done via Java Native Interface (JNI). The tool SWIG has been used to minimize the amount of boilerplate code that must be written for this interlanguage communication. The major benefit of this approach is that each iteration results in an executable that can be automatically compared with the outcome of the original simulation. This facilitates debugging of the C++ code as the number of added code lines remains manageable. Large parts of the spatial organization layer have already been ported using this procedure.

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Figure 1.2: Simulation Outcome of a Cultured Neural Network

1 Introduction

Cx3D is a simulation software built by the Institute of Neuroscience of the University of Zurich and ETH Zurich to simulate neural development [1].

The developmental approach of Cx3D is different from the Human Brain Project. More precisely, it is possible to grow sophisticated structures emerging from simple rules. This rules represent the genetic code of the virtual neuron. Figure 1.2 for example shows the simulation outcome of a cultured neural network.

Furthermore, a collection of videos can be found on youtube visualizing the chronology of the simulation.

- Lamination of a Column of Mouse Cerebral Cortex¹
- Simulation of a Self-Organizing Neural Network using Axonal Growth Rules²

1.1 Cx3D Architecture

This section describes the structure of Cx3D and its four layers of abstraction. Complexity is hidden in lower layers, making the whole simulation package easier to use. The user mainly interacts with the top most layers and has to call some methods from layer three. The

¹<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9InvFfnAkus>

²<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=il2uc-ZUZQ4>

Figure 1.3: Architecture of Cx3D[2]

implementation of each of these layers can be found in a separate Java package. Figure 1.3 gives an overview about the different abstraction layers (B), important classes and their assignment to a layer (A) as well as different copying strategies for local biology modules if a cell divides or if an axon branches (C-F). [2] The following list describes the four layers of abstraction: [2] [3]

- **Cell**

There exists one unique instance of class `Cell` per neuron.

- **Local Biology**

Localized behaviour like movement, branching and production or detection of a guidance cue are specified on this layer. It represents the genetic code of the virtual neuron.

- **Physics**

Responsible for the simulation of physical properties of the cells like friction, elasticity as well as the diffusion process.

- **Spatial Organization**

Calculation of neighbouring relation between physical objects.

In the following report, focus will lie on the most technical layer – spatial organization. The neighbourhood relation is calculated using a Delaunay triangulation. For a planar

Figure 1.4: Dependency Diagram Spatial Organization Layer

object, a triangulation is the subdivision of this object into triangles. In a 3D space triangles become tetrahedra. [4] The Delaunay triangulation is a triangulation calculated under a constraint. For a planar object this constraint states, that a point must not lie within the circumcircle of any triangle in the triangulation. As a result the minimum angle of the triangles is maximized, thus avoiding skinny triangles. [5] Figure 1.4 shows the classes and interfaces of the spatial organization layer along with their dependencies. It can be seen on the first glance that classes are tightly coupled.

2 Development Environment

The temporary development name of this project is `cx3d-cpp` and is hosted on github³ This name will change in future.

`cx3d-cpp` is developed on a linux environment – It was tested on CERN CentOS 7⁴ but should also run on other distributions. To build it, the following software packages must be installed – the tested version number is in parenthesis.

³<https://github.com/breitwieser/cx3d-cpp/>

⁴<https://linux.web.cern.ch/linux/centos7/>

- JDK (openjdk 1.8.0.51)
Java Development Kit
- gcc
C++ compiler
- Maven (3.0.5)
Java build tool and dependency manager
- CMake (2.8.11)
C++ build tool
- SWIG (3.0.7)
Tool that eases the process of interfacing C++ from Java.
- libGMP (6.0.0-11)
Arbitrary precision library in C/C++. Used as C++ equivalent of `java.math.BigInteger`
- Doxygen (1.8.5-3) only needed to build the documentation
Compiles documentation based on comments in source files

In order to obtain the code and to build and run the tests, execute the following commands in your terminal:

```
1 git clone https://github.com/breitwieser/cx3d-cpp.git
2 cd cx3d-cpp
3 mvn clean test
```

To build the Doxygen documentation for the native C++ classes, execute the following command. After completion open `doc/html/index.html` in your browser.

```
1 cd cmake && ./build.sh && make doc
```

The folder structure of the projects' root directory can be seen in figure 2.5. The `cmake*` directories contain the configuration files for compiling the C++ code. Scripts to uncover bugs that have been introduced during the translation process are stored in `debug_scripts`. `doc` contains configuration files to build the documentation and also acts as destination for these generated files. Tools to ensure high code quality are compiled in `housekeeping`. The Maven configuration file is `pom.xml`, while `.travis.yml` configures the continuous integration service Travis⁵.

⁵<https://travis-ci.org/>

```
cx3d-cpp
├── cmake/
├── cmake_standalone/
├── cmake_wo_standalone/
├── debug_scripts/
├── doc/
├── LICENSE
├── pom.xml
├── README.md
├── src/
└── .travis.yml
```

Figure 2.5: Project Folder Structure

```
cx3d-cpp/housekeeping
├── cpplint
│   ├── cpplint.py
│   ├── README
│   └── runCppLint.sh
├── eclipse-cpp-google-style.xml
└── README
```

Figure 2.6: housekeeping Folder Structure

Figure 2.6 shows the directory `housekeeping` in more detail. `cx3d-cpp` uses the Google C++ style guide⁶ to ensure that the code base is manageable and readable. Ideally source files written by different developer should look “the same”. Furthermore, Google also provides tools that aid the developer in following the rules and could also be used to enforce them. Firstly, there is a source formatter for Eclipse which also works for IntelliJ using the “Eclipse Code Formatter” plugin. Moreover, there is also a linter that checks if the source files adhere to the standard. The script `runCppLint.sh` checks all source files that are staged for a git commit. These two tools could be combined in a git commit hook in the future. Commits would only be possible if the style checks are ok.

2.1 Build System

2.1.1 Maven

In a first step Cx3D was transformed into a Maven project. Maven is a Java build tool and dependency manager. It simplifies configuration by using the principle “convention over configuration”. Commands to build the project are standardized and also the `src` directory

⁶<https://google.github.io/styleguide/cppguide.html>

Figure 2.7: Maven src Folder Structure

structure looks the same for all Maven projects – figure 2.7. For the person building a Maven project, this means that it is only required to learn a small set of commands to build **any** Maven project, and the configuration file (`pom.xml`), which stands for Project Object Model (POM), will ensure they get the results they desired. Listing 1 shows a few sample commands. Another very valuable feature is dependency management. All required libraries that are used by the project are specified in the configuration file. Maven downloads them automatically from a central repository and adds them to the classpath. How to add the library `gson` and `junit` as dependencies can be observed in listing 2.

```
1 # remove all build artefacts
2 mvn clean
3 # compile project
4 mvn compile
5 # compiles project and runs unit tests
6 mvn test
7 # compiles project, runs unit tests and e.g. packages the application in a jar file
8 mvn package
9 # compiles project and runs a specific test
10 mvn -Dtest=IntracellularDiffusionTest test
11 ...
```

Listing 1: Maven Command Examples

```
1 <dependencies>
2   <dependency>
3     <groupId>junit</groupId>
4     <artifactId>junit</artifactId>
5     <version>4.12</version>
6     <scope>test</scope>
7   </dependency>
8   <!-- object serialization -->
9   <dependency>
10    <groupId>com.google.code.gson</groupId>
11    <artifactId>gson</artifactId>
12    <version>2.3.1</version>
```

```
13 </dependency>  
14 </dependencies>
```

Listing 2: pom.xml Code Snippet

2.1.2 CMake

CMake is a cross-platform build system used to compile the native code. It does not automatically download dependencies, but detects them if they are installed on the system. The configuration file is named `CMakeLists.txt` and can be found in one of the `cmake*` directories – see figure 2.8. The main one is (`cmake`), while the others are used only in tricky situations during development or debugging. To generate a Makefile execute `cmake .` inside the `cmake` directory. Issue the build by running `make`. This two steps are combined in the `build.sh` shell script. The folder `modules` contains extensions to CMake for functionality that is not provided out of the box – e.g. detecting the arbitrary precision arithmetic library GMP.

```
cx3d-cpp/cmake  
├─ build.sh  
├─ CMakeLists.txt  
├─ modules  
└─ FindGMP.cmake
```

Figure 2.8: CMake Folder Structure

2.1.3 Marrying Maven and CMake

Creating the final runnable requires compiling the native code to a shared library followed by the compilation of the Java code. To make this process more convenient for the developer, the two build systems have been combined. Maven is wearing the breeches in this “relationship”. This means that CMake related tasks are integrated into the Maven lifecycle and automatically executed. This integration is done in the `pom.xml`⁷ file. The Maven commands stay the same (`mvn clean`, `mvn compile`, etc.).

2.2 Continues Integration Builds

Continues Integration (CI) Builds are an important tool to maintain high code quality. After each commit to the master branch of the git repository, the CI server checks out the code and runs the test suite using `mvn test`. This keeps the master branch clean and gives

⁷<https://github.com/breitwieser/cx3d-cpp/commit/041ecfafbf4e4066bef2b0f27d20c103b375747f>

the developer immediate feedback if the code changes also run on another machine. As an example it would detect if the developer forgot to add a source file to the repository.

A popular vendor of CI is Travis. For open source projects they offer this service for free. It is easy to configure as it integrates well with github. Configuration is done in the file `.travis.yml`. At the time of writing it is not possible to build the C++ part, because the configuration file does not contain the instructions to install some requirements (tools, libraries) yet.

3 Testing Framework

Ensuring correctness of the ported code is of great importance. Unfortunately, Cx3D does not come with any automated tests. As a result, a custom solution had to be developed. It checks that the C++ version has the same simulation outcome as the initial Java implementation. In this process, the whole simulation software is treated as a black box. Tutorial simulations that ship with Cx3D as well as simulations from publications were transformed into test cases. These test cases were executed using the original Java version. The simulation state of all these tests was persisted to disk, forming the ground truth. The result of the native implementation can now be compared against it. Furthermore, the testing framework measures execution times of these test cases, to track performance. All these tasks (setting up the environment, running the test, asserting the result and tracking performance) is performed in the class `BaseSimulationTest`⁸. Figure 3.9 shows the code coverage report for the simulation tests. It covers the most important parts.

Transforming the existing simulation into a test case is done in a breeze: Extend from the `BaseSimulationTest` class and replace the main method with `public void simulate()` – see `src/test/ini/cx3d/simulations/`.

Serializing the simulation state had to be developed as well. Although export features are integrated into Cx3d, they could not be used, because they did not meet the requirements for this task:

- Serialization should not contain implementation details
e.g. which Map implementation was used, or the state of a lock.
- It must be possible to generate the serialization in Java and C++ with the same result.

Tools like Gson have been evaluated, but discarded in the end, because they were not flexible enough. Gson is a Java Serialization Library that converts Java Objects into their JSON representation [6]. Finally, a custom solution has been developed that transforms the simulation state into JSON format.

⁸<https://github.com/breitwieser/cx3d-cpp/blob/dev/portSpatialOrganization/src/test/java/ini/cx3d/BaseSimulationTest.java>

cx3d

Element	Missed Instructions	Cov.	Missed Branches	Cov.	Missed	Cxty	Missed	Lines	Missed	Methods	Missed	Classes	
ini.cx3d.parallelSpatialOrganization		0%		0%	1,639	1,639	4,180	4,180	555	555	44	44	
ini.cx3d.graphics		26%		10%	364	403	1,149	1,604	123	155	8	19	
ini.cx3d.spatialOrganization		53%		48%	588	1,055	1,183	2,579	127	322	4	23	
ini.cx3d.physics		61%		56%	293	623	919	2,634	119	306	1	10	
ini.cx3d.utilities		18%		10%	241	280	594	713	75	100	4	7	
ini.cx3d.utilities.export		0%		0%	65	65	319	319	47	47	6	6	
ini.cx3d.simulations		45%		41%	128	191	276	549	65	106	0	2	
ini.cx3d.synapses		33%		46%	48	82	158	257	32	57	2	9	
ini.cx3d.localBiology		63%		61%	45	109	110	309	27	73	0	4	
ini.cx3d.cells		40%		29%	34	53	85	155	24	41	2	4	
ini.cx3d		81%		62%	12	37	26	115	5	20	0	2	
Total		47,695 of 70,312	32%	4,193 of 5,504	24%	3,457	4,537	8,999	13,414	1,199	1,782	71	130

Figure 3.9: Code Coverage

Changes in this serialization implementation or added test cases require the regeneration of the ground truth. Therefore a switch in `pom.xml`⁹ was integrated that helps the developer to do that – property: `updateSimStateReferenceFiles`.

Finally, a few words on performance tracking: In the beginning, `BaseSimulationTest` was designed to fail a test if it takes longer than the previous commit (with some margin). Development showed, that this was not a good idea, as it does not take the overhead of interlanguage method calls between Java and C++ Code into account. This means, that performance can drop dramatically due to communication overhead that is not related to the performance of the ported C++ code. Once porting has been finished, this overhead evaporates. Therefore, it was changed to log execution times instead of asserting it.

4 Iterative Porting Approach

Now that the development environment has been set-up, the next big decision is about the porting strategy. The two options are:

- Porting in one go
- Iterative porting

The first option means that class after class is translated, but no executable is available that can run a simulation until **all** code has been ported. The other alternative replaces a Java class with the native implementation. After each of those iterations an executable can be run to ensure if the simulation still works. This captures bugs early and limits the lines of code where the bug can “hide”.

Porting it in one go would lead to a debugging nightmare in the end, especially in the absence of any unit test. Therefore, the only reasonable choice is to use the “iterative porting approach”.

⁹<https://github.com/breitwieser/cx3d-cpp/blob/d1182c8b3af82472637cf961b669b117852adb63/pom.xml#L14>

Figure 4.10: Iterative Porting Approach Overview

Figure 4.10 shows it in more detail. Firstly, the developer picks a Java class with few dependencies, thus minimizing development effort and runtime overhead. In step two, the remaining Java application is refactored. For debugging purposes it is very helpful to quickly switch between the Java and native implementation. Therefore, it is necessary to extract a common interface of this class and only use the interface in the remaining program. Object creation is done using a factory which also routes calls to static methods accordingly. Afterwards, the Java code is translated into its C++ representation. In the next step, code that enables communication between Java and C++ has to be written. Upon completion the tests are run. If they pass the developer can continue with the next class until the whole application has been ported.

This procedure is straightforward. The step that probably needs more clarification is the communication between Java and C++. The Java Virtual Machine (JVM) comes with a feature called Java Native Interface (JNI) to support interfacing native code. Writing all the intermediary JNI code oneself can be cumbersome. Fortunately there is a tool called SWIG¹⁰ that connects code written in C/C++ with other high-level programming languages such as Java. It can be seen as a compiler, that takes the C++ headers as input and generates four output files (figure 4.11). Another input are “SWIG Customizations” that modify the generated code. SWIG is designed to be minimally invasive. This means that the ordinary C++ files normally do not contain SWIG specific code. This attribute is especially helpful as source files must not be edited after porting has been finished.

¹⁰<http://www.swig.org/>

Figure 4.11: Schema of the Tool SWIG

In the example of figure 4.11, `Widget.java` is a proxy that replaces the original Java implementation. This proxy forwards the calls to the native method definitions that can be found in `moduleJNI.java`. In Java there is no such thing as a global context like in C. Therefore, its Java equivalent is stored in `module.java`. It can also contain code that simplifies type conversions. The first three files are Java code. The last one `moduleJAVA_wrap.cxx` contains all the C++ JNI boilerplate code. In SWIG it is necessary to group classes in modules. These modules have a name that replace the string `module` in the example in figure 4.11.

Caveat during Step 2: `Cx3D` often uses object identity comparisons to decide if two objects are equal – `if(a == b)`. The Java proxy class used to interface the C++ implementation breaks this code, because this lightweight object is often destroyed and recreated. Therefore, it is necessary to replace this with `if(java.util.Objects.equals(a, b))`.

4.1 Source Folder Structure Revisited

This chapter shows how the native source files are integrated into the Maven folder tree. Figure 4.12 shows an illustration. One can see that there is a new folder under `src/main` called `cpp`. It splits up the source files into headers (`include`) and implementation (`src`). All SWIG customizations reside in directory `swig`.

SWIG's generated Java files are written into the existing Maven-Java src tree (`src/main/java/package/` while the compiled shared libraries are stored inside the `resource` folder.

Figure 4.12: src Directory Structure – “SWIG View”

4.2 Build Revisited

Before going into details of SWIG, it is best to describe the whole build process including the tool SWIG – see figure 4.13. The developer issues a build using the command `mvn compile` or `mvn test` that implicitly compiles the code. Before Maven compiles the Java code it calls `cmake/build.sh` that runs the CMake build. CMake in turn, calls SWIG which generates / or updates the missing Java and C++ files. Afterwards CMake generates a shared library for each SWIG module and places them in the `/src/main/resource` folder. Then control is returned to Maven which finally compiles the Java code leading to an executable version of Cx3D. Please note that SWIG as well as C++ files have a preprocessor.

4.3 SWIG Customizations

SWIG customizations are used to modify the code generation process. In order to better understand this section I highly recommended to read the SWIG documentation¹¹ especially the following chapters: Introduction, SWIG Basics, Typemaps and Java Support. The following tasks are achieved using SWIG customizations:

- Rules for type conversions and type modifications
e.g. function with parameter `const std::array<std::shared_ptr<Rational>, 3>&` that should translate into `Rational[]` on the Java side
- Two-way-communication
e.g. Java defined callback that is passed on to the native implementation and invoked from there.
- Switches
to change between Java and native implementation of a class, or to turn on debugging

¹¹<http://www.swig.org/Doc3.0/Sections.html#Sections>

Figure 4.13: Build Step Schema

output for a class

The files for these customizations are stored inside `src/main/cpp/swig/`. Below is a list describing their purpose:

- `class_customizations/`
This directory contains a file for each class that contains the necessary customizations. This keeps the module file clean.
- `big_integer_typemap.i`, `cx3d_shared_ptr.i`, `primitives.i`, `std_array_typemap.i` and `std_list_typemap.i`
Specifies how types are converted between Java and C++.
- `list_iterator_cpp.h`
Helper class to convert `std::list` to `java.util.List`.
- `cx3d.i` and `spatial_organization.i`
SWIG module files
- `load_library.i`
Automatically load native library at program start
- `util.i`
Contains customization for Java and native defined classes and for debugging.
- `generate_java_interface.i`
Legacy code to enable two way communication.

4.3.1 Native Defined Class

The term “native defined class” (NDC) denotes a class whose C++ implementation is used at runtime. In other words, a ported class. Therefore, the SWIG macro `%native_defined_class` in file `util.i` is used. It inserts code that implements the Java `equals` method and forwards the call to the C++ method `bool equalTo(const Type& other)`. This method is important to compare two objects in Java. Furthermore, it inserts an empty default constructor and an empty implementation of `registerJavaObject` into the generated Java proxy class. Lastly, it inserts the static boolean variable `useNativeCLASS_NAME` into `module.java` and sets it to true. The tasks in the last two sentences are necessary in order to quickly switch between implementations. For more details see chapter 4.3.3.

4.3.2 Java Defined Class

Equivalent to a NDC, a “Java defined class” (JDC) denotes a class whose Java implementation is used at runtime. When is this needed?

During normal porting operations, if a class is ported which has references to other classes that have not been ported yet. The idea of the iterative porting approach is to port one class at a time. Therefore, there must be a mechanism that allows a redirection from a C++ call to Java. Furthermore, it must be possible that a NDC returns a Java object. An example is the commit¹² of the class `Triangle3D`. Class `SpaceNode` has not been ported yet, but the methods `getPosition` and `getId` are called from the C++ side. As you can see in this commit, it is sufficient to create a scaffold of this class without the actual implementation. The method bodies are never executed. The macro `%java_defined_class` takes care that calls to this methods get redirected to the Java implementation. It uses the SWIG director feature to achieve cross language polymorphism. If a director is specified for a class, SWIG automatically generates a subclass from it containing re-implementations of all public virtual methods. If a function of a NDC returns a JDC, there must be a mapping between the pointer used on the native side and the actual Java object. This is done using a Map (`javaObjectMap`) inside the Java proxy class. The actual Java class subclasses the proxy class and calls `registerJavaObject(this)` in its constructors. Thus, this object can easily be retrieved using the function `getJavaObject` from the Java proxy class using the C++ pointer as argument.

The second use case is switching between native and Java implementation for debugging purposes.

4.3.3 Switching between Native and Java Implementation and Debugging Output

The JDC and NDC implementations were designed in a way that it is possible to switch between them without code modifications. This also applies for turning the debugging output

¹²<https://github.com/breitwieser/cx3d-cpp/commit/f02e46acd826f4ae5e2df925849c312532068bd2>

on or off. This is essential for an efficient debugging process – see next chapter for more details.

The only change that has to be made is in the administration area of the SWIG module file – e.g. `spatial_organization.i`¹³. If the native implementation should be used insert the line `%native(CLASS_NAME_CAPS)`. It defines a SWIG preprocessor variable that is used inside a conditional – e.g. `edge.i`¹⁴

Debugging output for a class is generated if `%debug(CLASS_NAME_CAPS)` was called. On the Java side it sets the boolean variable `debugCLASS_NAME` to true. On the C++ side it uses the preprocessor definition `CLASS_NAME_DEBUG` that alters the compiled code e.g. `edge.h`¹⁵

5 Debugging

As mentioned in chapter 4.2 the build process involves quite some code generation and modification until it is compiled. First the SWIG preprocessor is called followed by SWIG file generation succeeded by the C++ preprocessor. While debugging issues in the generated code it can be very helpful to edit these files manually and compile without overriding these changes. For this purpose a separate CMake build definition has been created and can be found in the folder `cake_wo_swig`. It compiles the shared libraries without overriding `moduleJAVA_wrap.cxx` Once the issue has been resolved it can be backtracked and integrated into the code generation process.

Furthermore, there is a CMake configuration to build a standalone application from the native source files.

If the code compiles successfully, but the test fails, the issue can be categorized into three groups. The following classification also contains a strategy to fix the bug.

- **Java cannot load the native library or crashes while creating the first object**
Test constructing this object on the C++ side in a main method and use `cmake_standalone` to compile it. There might be an implementation of a method or constructor missing.
- **JVM crashes**
Have a look at the generated `hs_err_pid*.log` file. It points to the function causing the issue. If the issue is in the glue code, try to fix it there directly and compile using `cmake_wo_swig`. After it has been fixed, integrate it into the SWIG code generation process.
- **Simulation outcome is different or throws Exception**
Use debugging framework to identify the issue.

¹³https://github.com/breitwieser/cx3d-cpp/blob/dev/portSpatialOrganization/src/main/cpp/swig/spatial_organization.i#L12

¹⁴https://github.com/breitwieser/cx3d-cpp/blob/dev/portSpatialOrganization/src/main/cpp/swig/class_customization/edge.i#L46

¹⁵https://github.com/breitwieser/cx3d-cpp/blob/dev/portSpatialOrganization/src/main/cpp/include/spatial_organization/edge.h#L62

5.1 Debugging Framework

The debugging solution solves the problem that often execution paths diverge after thousands of method calls resulting in a different simulation outcome or an exception. Therefore, identifying the bug is like finding a needle in the haystack. As a result, it is wise to build a strong magnet to aid the developer during this process.

The system is designed to generate debugging statements for the Java and C++ class. After the test case is run with the two implementations the output files can be inspected for differences.

What kind of output is needed to reliably find bugs?

- all method calls with parameters
- inner state before method call
- inner state after method call
- method return value
- (all calls to other objects from within the CPC with parameter and inner state)

If all this information is logged it should avoid false negatives (no differences between Java and C++ debugging output, but a failing test case). The last one is in parenthesis, because it can be achieved by turning on debugging output for all classes whose methods are called from the CPC. Therefore it is sufficient to consider the first four points in the implementation.

5.1.1 Implementation

The debugging framework was developed in two versions. At first it was implemented using a Dynamic Java Proxy. The Proxy is dynamically created and intercepts all method calls. The inception handler creates the debugging statements and delegates the method call to the “real” object. The main benefit of this solution is that it does not require modifications if a new class is introduced because the proxy is generated at runtime. Due to the following limitations it was necessary to update the implementation.

- Only works for Java calling C++ (misses C++ to C++ and C++ to Java calls)
- Proxy is sometimes “lost” (e.g. CPC method calling another one and passing itself as a parameter)
- Does not capture nested method calls

Version two of the debugging framework uses subclassing to create the debugging output. Code listing 3 shows the principle on a code snippet from `debug/tetrahedron_debug.h`¹⁶.

¹⁶https://github.com/breitwieser/cx3d-cpp/blob/dev/portSpatialOrganization/src/main/cpp/include/spatial_organization/debug/tetrahedron_debug.h#L51

All methods are overridden in the subclass. Due to polymorphism the debugging implementation gets called. It generates the output, calls the actual implementation in the base class before logging the return value and inner state after the method call. In contrast to the Java Proxy solution this requires manual work every time a new class or method is introduced and whenever the signature of a method changes. On the other hand, it is the most flexible solution and resolves all limitations of V1, mentioned above. What is more, due to the fixed structure of the debugging class, it can be generated by an IDE and postprocessed using regular expressions to automate this process. This has not been fully implemented yet.

```
1 bool isInsideSphere(const std::array<double, 3>& point) override {
2     logCall(point);
3     auto ret = Tetrahedron<T>::isInsideSphere(point);
4     logReturn(ret);
5     return ret;
6 }
```

Listing 3: Debug Output Generation Example

5.1.2 Usage

To use the debugging framework set the debug switch in the SWIG module description for the currently ported class (CPC) true and generate the debugging output for Java.

```
1 mvn -Dtest=IntracellularDiffusionTest test | grep DBG >java
```

Then switch to the native implementation (chapter 4.3.3) and run again. This time writing the output to a different file:

```
1 mvn -Dtest=IntracellularDiffusionTest test | grep DBG >cpp
```

In the next step we inspect the generated files for differences. The IDE IntelliJ has a very good diff-tool to do that, but of course it is also possible to use the `diff` command within the terminal. Thereby, we come up against the problem that the output files are many thousand lines long – too large for the IntelliJ diff tool for example. As already mentioned in the beginning of this section, the first difference is often found after thousands of method calls of the CPC. Therefore, a shell script was created to split the large files into junks and find the one that contains the first difference:

```
1 debugging_solution/find_first_diff.sh java cpp
```

This script generates two files (`java_page` and `cpp_page`) that contain the page with the first difference. Figure 5.14 shows a screenshot of the IntelliJ diff tool revealing an error in the `equals` method that lead to a different execution path and therefore different simulation outcomes.

Sometimes it is helpful to know where the method with the difference was called from. This can be achieved by setting a conditional breakpoint at the function that generates the output and exploring the call stack after the breakpoint was hit – see figure 5.15.

Figure 5.14: Difference in Debugging Output between Java and C++

Figure 5.15: Conditional Breakpoint – In IntelliJ this dialog can be opened by right-clicking on a breakpoint

Another problem is spurious differences. This means that there are differences in the Java and C++ debug output files even though calculations are the same. Figure 5.16 gives an example of this behaviour. The JVM executes the method `getPosition` in opposite order as the equivalent C++ code. This deteriorates the signal to noise ratio, making it very difficult to find the real differences. Therefore, it is necessary to change the Java code to avoid this spurious differences.

6 Project Status

Diagram 6.17 shows the already completed classes in green and classes that are currently ported in orange. At the moment, performance suffers substantially, because there is a huge overhead due to the extensive communication between classes in different languages. This overhead comes from the fact that the central class `SpaceNode` is still implemented in Java, while e.g. `Tetrahedron` has already been ported. These classes communicate extensively with each other leading to a large overhead in interlanguage method calls and type conversions.

6.1 Performance Analysis

After recognizing the performance problems an analysis has been carried out. Running the `IntracellularDiffusionTest` there are 28 million method calls from Java to C++ and 25 million in the other direction. A quick benchmark showed that especially calls from C++ into Java code are expensive. They are 17 times slower as they use reflection. After the class `SpaceNode` has been ported, the calls to Java will be reduced to 0.8M and 35k if the whole spatial organization layer is available in C++. Thus, overhead from interlanguage calls will reduce dramatically, bringing the performance back on track.

7 Conclusion

This report showed how to port an application from Java to C++. It introduced a testing framework to prove correctness of the resulting C++ code as well as a debugging framework that helps the developer to find bugs. The iterative porting approach has been proven successful and is the state of the art to translate a large application. Although it has some shortcomings, the tool SWIG was very helpful in this process.

```

1 double[] [] positions = new double[] [] {
2     adjacentNodes[0].getPosition(),
3     adjacentNodes[1].getPosition(),
4     adjacentNodes[2].getPosition(),
5     adjacentNodes[3].getPosition() };
    
```

(a) Original Java Version

```

1 for (size_t i = 0; i < adjacent_nodes_.size(); i++) {
2     positions[i] = adjacent_nodes_[i]->getPosition();
3 }
    
```

(b) Ported C++ Code

(c) Differences

Figure 5.16: Spurious Differences

Figure 6.17: Porting Progress of Spatial Organization Layer (green: completed, orange: in process)

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